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Mastery of the Competencies of Edukasyon Sa Pagpapakatao (ESP)

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Abstract

The study determined the mastery of competencies of Grade 6 learners in the Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao (ESP) subject. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following queries: What is the student's mastery level of the ESP competencies? Does ESP competency mastery significantly differ if learners are categorized according to geographic locations? What competencies are least manifested by the students? What could enhancement scheme be designed to raise students' mastery of competencies? This work was conducted during the SY 2019-2020 to selected public elementary schools in Ubay III, Southwest District, with 105 grade six students. The research used convergent-parallel quantitative design to determine the mastery of learning competencies of Grade 6 students. The researcher used the Gabay sa Kurikulum ng K to 12 Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao Grade 6 competencies. The questionnaire was supplemented with interviews to verify the responses of the respondents. In the analysis and interpretation of data, a weighted mean was used. The research found that students have mastered most of the competencies except for the competency "showing the relevance of spirituality on developing one's personality." There was little difference in mastery level of the competencies of those students living along the highway compared to those living in mountainous areas. The researcher concluded that a strong foundation of values education at home, in school, and community is vital in the formation of the students. This study recommended that the teachers, school administrators, and DepEd officials should work together to shape the moral values of all Filipino students and ensure that the students have mastered all ESP competencies. An enhancement scheme is made to address the need to improve these ESP competencies' manifestation.

Keywords: *edukasyon sa pagpapakatao, competencies, mastery level, k to 12 curriculum*

Introduction

Providing moral education is fundamental and vital in educating the youth. It is imperative to build a nation with its citizens being morally grounded. Without a strong foundation on the norms of right or wrong, a student could become a corrupt political leader, a horrifying criminal, or an irresponsible and uncaring citizen. Department of Education (DepEd) may seem an elusive vision, but one life touched through Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao (ESP) would make a big difference (Okabe, 2013).

Moreover, this objective is currently challenging due to technological and other influences. In the current generation, youth values are gradually disappearing, and there is a crisis in character formation. It is also believed that since character formation occurs primarily during childhood, it is the responsibility of the educational system to provide character-building education.

Values education is the procedure of teaching and learning about socially valued ideals. This learning can take various forms, but the ultimate goal is for students to comprehend the values, demonstrate them through their attitudes and actions, and contribute to society through good citizenship and ethical conduct (Lovat,

2009).

ESP is taught in both elementary and secondary schools as a core subject. It is accorded the same importance as major disciplines like English, Science, and Math. It is now a distinct subject, not only a component of other subject areas. It is a course that educates students with the requisite prudence and moral responsibility to govern their life choices. It focuses on attitude, morality, ethics, values, and qualities to live by (Bardos-Villamor, Camari, & Palmes, 2015).

The school is of great importance when it comes to the moral-cognitive development of the pupils. There is an urgent need to improve the quality of ESP education currently prevalent in our country (Bowe, Ball & Gold, 2017). Since some students and teachers took it for granted and viewed it as an additional responsibility, many failed to see its actual value. Occasionally, the allocated time for the topic was taken for school cleaning and other co-curricular and extra-curricular activities. Consequently, the competencies remained incomplete at the end of the academic year (DMEA Report, 2017).

Since ESP is still taken for granted at this time, it is necessary to analyze the subject's significance. Without ESP, the fundamental concept of life, which is

to develop a sense of justice and the fulfillment of human dignity, could never be attained. In order to comprehend and apply this fundamental principle, the curriculum guide's required competencies must be met. With this, moral issues such as illegal narcotics, rape cases, prostitution, horrific homicides, human trafficking, abortions, physical violence, graft and corruption, and terrorism, to name a few, might be reduced or eradicated (Adarlo, 2017). DepEd has prepared a set of competencies to be developed among the pupils in the ESP subject. These competencies emphasize the development of the individual's physical, social, emotional, mental, and moral formation through inner transformation. It consists of cognitive, behavioral, and emotional elements. It starts with the student's understanding of his responsibility to himself, his family, his community, his nation, the world, and God and then progresses to decision-making and responsible behavior.

The researcher has observed that children no longer manifest the value of respect. The good manners which are reflective of Filipino culture are starting to deteriorate. Hence, the researcher would like to look into how these competencies stipulated in the curriculum are observed in school and to what level the students manifest these. Moreover, through this study, the researcher can identify which of the listed competencies need more enhancement in terms of strategies and approaches. This study's findings will be used to enhance the pedagogy in teaching ESP.

Research Questions

The study determined the level of competencies of the learners in ESP of Grade 6 students. The study's findings served as the basis for a proposed enhancement scheme in teaching Values Education. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following:

1. What is the student's mastery level of the ESP competencies?
2. Does the mastery level of ESP competencies significantly differ if learners are categorized according to geographic locations?
3. What enhancement scheme could be designed to raise students' mastery of competencies?

Literature Review

This research is grounded in Shalom H. Schwartz's (2012) Theory of Basic Values. This hypothesis demonstrates that values have always been a prominent term in the social sciences. The central

concept of the theory is that values form a circular structure that represents the motivations of each value.

In addition, the Theory of Basic Values is reinforced by Bandura's Social Learning Theory, referenced by King (2010), which asserts that children acquire desirable behavior patterns through rewards and punishments and imitation. According to them, imitation is crucial for learning both aberrant and desirable conduct. Both cross-cultural and laboratory studies support the claim that rather than receiving explicit instructions, moral and other behaviors are acquired via seeing the elder's behavior. Children learn more by emulating what their elders do than by doing what their elders request. The youngster learns by witnessing how the parents and other individuals interact with and treat others.

Bandura's results are applicable even in preventing an individual from committing immoral conduct. Bandura's social learning theory implies that children may learn to inhibit unwanted behavior just as well or perhaps better by observing a model. The child's behavior begins to submit to his authority gradually.

The child incorporates the externally imposed rules of behavior into his behavior. A kid learns moral behavior through direct and indirect exposure to the dread of punishment (moral anxiety). Society contributes by providing and expanding learning opportunities beyond what peers and neighborhood groups provide at home. It is challenging to predict moral behavior in conditions without the possibility of punishment or reward (Jarvis, 2012).

Shaver (1976) established a jurisprudential paradigm of moral instruction based on his Rational Building Theory. This idea illuminates the various aspects of morality, such as judging, caring, curing, and acting. Its principal focus is on judicial matters. It can serve as a guide for teachers who wish to implement a moral education program in schools. In this theory, Shaver stressed the importance of instructors and students in the classroom for character development and the formation of moral ideals.

As in moral education, the rational building theory has substantial concerns regarding the role of critical reflection on teachers and students. It emphasizes the necessity of teaching the unique analytic skills fundamental to democratic citizenship. It presents not just a program for moral education but also specific essential considerations that are directly important to moral education. These factors include identifying, clarifying, analyzing label generalization on value conflicts, and making informed decisions.

The K-12 curriculum, as expressed in the ESP curriculum guide, emphasizes the significance of values and moral development for students. The competencies were oriented on utilizing and valuing resources and means of subsistence with accountability and duty. Another is taking the necessary steps to assist in making a family-beneficial decision. One more is taking satisfaction in the quality of the job based on standards. Another ability is displaying rigorous adherence to national and international environmental protection rules and innovation in developing any initiative that will aid and inspire the nation's development. For Filipinos, freedom must come with corresponding obligations and constraints. Another skill involves demonstrating the significance of being responsible to others, fostering conformity with national and international rules, and demonstrating the significance/role of spirituality in personality development (DepEd Curriculum Guide, 2016).

The Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013, also known as Republic Act 10533, emphasizes that the K to 12 Curriculum, which includes ESP, is based on the spiral development concept. To set an example, ESP instructors must both teach and practice the cognitive dimension of values and virtues. The Department of Education Order No. 41, Series 2003, entitled "Values Education in the Basic Education Curriculum," encourages the influential role of every teacher in bolstering the Department's collective efforts in developing desirable values among students and evaluating the outcomes of interventions conducted outside the classroom.

The ESP standard for the sixth-grade curriculum emphasizes that students are expected to demonstrate an understanding of the competencies that can help them elevate their dignity, love for others, and ethical actions and decisions toward a peaceful and abundant life for the welfare of all humanity (Grade 6 Curriculum Guide, 2016). In addition, the competencies and framework of ESP are founded on two distinct disciplines: ethics and career guidance. Ethics is the study of human morality in action.

Similarly, Career Guidance assists students in determining which academic courses, arts, sports, or technical-vocational fields best match their skills and interests (Parojenog, 2020). These competencies are intended to shape each student's ethical standards. To do this, students are expected to master the subject's five macro-skills: pag-unawa, pagninilay, pagpapasya and pagkilos. (DepEd Curriculum Guide, 2016). ESP is structured in the classroom according to the ever-

changing societal and national demands. Educational systems and teachers play a crucial role in forming the individual's life patterns, of which values are crucial (Alonzo, 2015).

Every grade level is required to take ESP as a subject in every public school. Before passing a topic, each grade level has matching competencies that students must attain. DepEd published *Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao Gabay Pangkurikulum* last December 2013, containing the relevant information regarding the subject (Almonte-Acosta, 2011). Society, schools, and educators must perform a variety of roles in light of changing circumstances and curricula. The K-12 curriculum outlined in *Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao* (2013) is comprehensive and should be applied nationwide. The individual's life will be impacted by the manifestation of the ESP competencies and the actual application of these values (Sanderse, 2013).

Methodology

Research Design

To attain the purpose of this study, the researcher used the convergent-parallel quantitatively design to investigate the mastery of learning competencies manifested by Grade 6 students. The researcher used the *Gabay sa Kurikulum ng K to 12 Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao Grade 6* (2016) competencies as the content of the researcher-made questionnaire to measure mastery and describe their learning competencies.

Environment

Ubay is the locale of the study. The research environment is further divided according to the geographic location of the respondents, like along the highway or mountainous regions. In the province of Bohol, the town of Ubay is a first-class municipality. It is approximately 124 kilometers northeast of Tagbilaran City, the province's sole capital. It is the largest municipality in Bohol, with a total land area of approximately 292.05 hectares.

The municipality has 44 public elementary schools, one in each barangay and one on Tres Reyes Island. The municipality is divided into three educational districts: Ubay I (North District), Ubay II (East District), and Ubay III (Southwest District). Since the researcher is stationed in Ubay III, this study focuses on that district. The schools are divided into locations such as highways or mountainous areas using

disproportionate random sampling and multi-stage sampling. The elementary schools found along the national highway are Ilihan, San Pascual, and Lomangog, wherein there is convenience and accessibility. On the other hand, Hambabauran, Pag-asa, and Villa Teresita are in mountainous areas characterized by rocky roads and less accessible transportation and communication.

Participants

Randomly stratified, disproportionate, and multi-stage sampling was used on the grade 6 students at public elementary schools in Ubay III, Southwest District, namely, Hambabauran Elementary School, Ilihan Elementary School, Lomangog Elementary School, Pag-asa Elementary School, San Pascual Elementary School, and Villa Teresita Elementary School. The participants were one hundred five (105) grade 6 students.

Table 1. *Research Participants*

School	Students	Percentage (%)
HambabauranES	15	14
Ilihan ES	15	14
Lomangog ES	15	14
Pag-asa ES	15	14
San Pascual ES	30	28
Villa Teresita ES	15	14
Total	105	100

Instrument

The researcher-made questionnaire is based on the ESP competencies listed in the Curriculum Guide of Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao (2016) provided by the Department of Education. The questionnaire listed the competencies indicators, which the respondents checked as responses. It was given to the twenty (20) Grade 6 students at California Elementary School, where the researcher is stationed. The questionnaire was supplemented with an interview to validate the participants' responses.

Research Procedure

In gathering the data, a letter of permission to conduct the study was given to the Dean of the College of Advanced Studies, the School President, the Schools Division Superintendent, Division of Bohol. Another letter is given to school Principals to conduct the study on the competencies of Edukasyon Sa Pagpapakatao

(ESP) of Grade 6 students in Ubay III, Southwest District of the School Year 2019-2020. With the persons mentioned above' approval, the questionnaire was distributed to the respondents. Questionnaires were distributed to 105 respondents; 15 students were chosen for each school, and 30 were from San Pascual ES. The items were explained to the respondents before they answered the questions.

Results

This study sought to determine the mastery level of the learners in ESP of Grade 6 students, the School Year 2019-2020, with the end of making an enhancement scheme. The data from the variables are herein presented in response to the different problems of the study. Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao (ESP) practice in one's personal life promotes unity in thoughts, words, and actions. Formation of character starts as early as primary grades.

Here, learners are taught to make wise decisions and devise deliberate choices so that these choices will lead him/her to a better quality of life. The teaching of Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao (ESP) has cognitive, behavioral, and affective dimensions. It begins with the student's understanding of responsibility to himself, his family, fellowmen, country, world, and God, laying the foundation for wise decision-making and responsible action.

The learning competencies are stipulated in the curriculum guide for Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao. The table presents an explanation and analysis of these competencies.

Table 2. *Mastery Level of Grade 6 Students in ESP Subject N=105*

Learning Competencies	Mean	Interpretation
1. Utilize and give value to resources and source of livelihood with accountability and responsibility (Nakapagami nang may pagpapahalaga at pananagutan sa kabuhatan at pinagkukunang-yaman)	3.05	Mastered
2. Do the right steps that can help make a decision that will benefit the family (Naisasagawa ang tamang hakbang na makatutulong sa pagtuo ng isang desisyon na makabuti sa pamilya)	3.03	Mastered
3. Acquire pride in the performance of quality of work based on standards (Naiipagmamalaki ang anumang natapos na gawain na nakasusunod sa pamantayan at kalidad)	3.01	Mastered
4. Demonstrate strict adherence to national and international laws on environmental protection (Nakapagpapakita ng tiyap na pagtutunod sa mga batas pambansa at pandaigdigang tungkol sa pangangalaga sa kapaligiran)	2.99	Mastered
5. Show creativity in creating any project that will help and serve as an inspiration to the country's development (Naiipapakita ang pagiging malikhain sa paggawa ng anumang proyekto na makatutulong at magaalibing inspirasyon tungo sa pag-unlad ng bansa)	2.98	Mastered
6. Give importance/Value basic freedoms with corresponding responsibilities and limitations (Nabibigyang-halaga ang mga salitang kalayaan na may kasukulang pananagutan at limitasyon)	2.96	Mastered
7. Give importance to good and successful Filipinos (Napaihalagahan ang magaling at matagumpay na mga Pilipino)	2.92	Mastered
8. Show the importance of being successful to others (Naiipakikita ang kahalagahan ng pagiging responsable sa kapwa)	2.90	Mastered
9. Promote compliance with national and international laws (Naisasakilos ang pagtutad sa mga batas pambansa at pandaigdigang)	2.84	Mastered
10. Show the relevance/role of spirituality on developing one's personality (Napatutunayan na nagpapaunlad ng pagkatao ang ispiritalidad)	2.40	Least-Mastered
Overall Weighted Mean	2.90	Mastered

Table 2 shows that most of the respondents are masters in the listed competencies except one competency. Hence, they differ in terms of mean values. The competency "Utilizing and giving value to resources

and source of livelihood with accountability and responsibility" emerged as the highest with a mean of 3.05, described as mastered. The result means that learners give importance to natural resources, which are the source of income for most of their parents. Most of their parents are farmers and fishermen. Students have mastered these competencies because the teacher has taught this. Furthermore, these pupils see how their parents sacrificed a lot so that they would be provided with their needs.

The learning competency of "Doing the right steps that can help make a decision that will benefit the family" got a mean of 3.03, described as mastered. This finding revealed that the culture of the Filipino family, which is family oriented, is still evident in society today. At this age, most of them still cling to their family in times of trouble. Consulting someone is a good move that they would learn to make a good decisions as they grow up. Learners need to have the ability to make decisions quickly and responsibly.

Furthermore, teachers need to teach students good decision-making skills. Students also learn to make decisions through experience. Learners should inculcate in their minds that they should use what they know to make wise decisions. When learners improve their decision-making skills, they increase their value in future undertakings, jobs, families, and communities.

Acquiring pride in the performance of quality of work based on standards competency has a mean of 3.01 and is still described as competent. This means that students feel happy and proud when they do their work, especially when they do it excellently. Hence, they were made to put into their service or product and produce something to be proud of. Every child in school is proud of the finished product or project, especially if it is done on his/her own.

Demonstrating strict adherence to national and international environmental protection laws has a value of 2.99. This means students act the proper way of taking care of the environment. They do the proper waste segregation of waste materials, follow simple traffic rules, and avoid pollution that can harm the environment. National and international laws can play a vital role in encouraging reuse and recycling by helping to create a market for "waste." Students can apply the 3Rs (reuse, reduce, and recycle) at home and school. In order to carry out environmental protection, people need to uphold and obey the laws made for nature.

The competency "Showing creativity in creating any

project that will help and serve as an inspiration to the country's development" got a mean of 2.98 with the descriptive interpretation of mastered. This denotes that the respondents are encouraged to the point of highlighting and showcasing their finished project. In order to develop creativity, the family, school, and government may start to emphasize it. From the beginning, the family and the school must cultivate these values in each member and student. Creativity can help discover new solutions to problems, whether personal or social. If it were not for the creative works of men, society would not have achieved comfort and prosperity.

Meanwhile, the competency "Giving importance/Value basic freedoms with corresponding responsibilities and limitations" got the mean of 2.96, described as mastered. The learners are still restricted to what is dictated by their parents. Though they have freedom, they cannot assert so much because they are still under their parent's control. Responsibility is being held accountable for one's actions. It might involve figuring out how to get paid for the work, owning one's mistake, or having others count on it. Freedom without responsibility is undoubtedly tempting, but few people will give that gig and take responsibility for one's work. Responsibility without freedom is stressful. There are plenty of works in school among students that somehow test their freedom coupled with responsibilities. When students are in doubt and stuck, they seek freedom, and the surest long-term route is to take more responsibilities.

Giving importance to good and successful Filipinos received a weighted mean of 2.92. It means that the youth have been called to emulate good and successful fellow citizens like our heroes.

Our national heroes demonstrated supreme patriotism and unwavering commitment to fighting for the protection and preservation of Filipino heritage. The progress, pride, and freedom these successful Filipinos bring in various fields are still the same challenges that students face as they strive for a strong, independent, and bountiful nation. Instilling a love of country at a young age will instill values such as discipline and organization and impart common sense to the next generation of Filipinos.

The competency "Showing the importance of being responsible to others" was described as mastered by a mean of 2.90. This means that responsibility is one of one's character traits, which means that a person can respond to his actions, take on some responsibilities, and face the consequences. Someone's irresponsibility

is not only annoying when a person cannot or does not want to perform their duties. This is admirable because many people will not deal with irresponsible people. People put their faith in others who can be relied on. A responsible person can be trusted to act without being closely monitored because he is accountable for his actions.

"Promoting compliance with national and international laws" is the competency that got the mean of 2.84 with the descriptive interpretation of mastered. A mean value that is lower than the rest. This implied that the laws and rules of man are for the good of man. It is a fact that we must bear in mind at times that we may be tempted to disobey our rules. For example, when we are tempted to cross the wrong lane just because there is no police guard, we should think that the proper crossing is there to ensure we can safely cross the road. Likewise, adherence to law and policy can hinder our progress. For example, the taxation of citizens is the source of every development and health project necessary for our country to flourish. In addition, obeying the people's law helps keep peace and order because when no one obeys the law, everyone lives in peace.

"Showing the relevance/role of spirituality on developing one's personality" is the competency that ranks last, with the mean of 2.40 interpreted as least mastered. This denoted that the spirituality and faith of each person play a significant role in shaping his excellent character. Because of our Godly feelings, our love for Him is shaped, and our desire to develop a good character develops. Developing love for God is not just gaining knowledge of God.

The average weighted of 2.90 is interpreted as mastered. It implies that the teaching of ESP is about developing virtues, good habits, and dispositions that lead to responsible and mature adulthood. Effective teaching and learning processes of ESP have to promote the development of virtues and values. These virtues and values are developed through practice.

Table 3. *Difference of Mastery Level in ESP competencies in Geographical Location N=105*

Geographical Location	Mean	Interpretation
1. Along the highway	2.91	Mastered
2. In Mountainous areas	2.89	Mastered

As reflected in the table, students living along the highway got an overall mean of 2.91, which is

interpreted as having mastered the competencies. In contrast, students living in mountainous areas got an overall mean of 2.89, described as mastered. This finding revealed a little difference in terms of mastery level in ESP leading the way in the students living along the highway. Schools along the highway have an advantage in supervision and school governance compared to mountainous areas. Moreover, schools along the highway have full-pledged school heads, unlike those in mountainous areas that only cluster schools into a based school.

Table 4. *Values/Competencies that are mastered N=105*

Learning Competencies	Mean	Interpretation
1. Show the relevance/role of spirituality on developing one's personality (Napatutunayan na nagpapaunlad ng pagkatao ang ispiritwalidad)	2.40	Least-Mastered
2. Promote compliance with national and international laws (Naisasakilos ang pagtupad sa mga batas pambansa at pandaigdigang)	2.84	Mastered

As reflected in the table, "Prove that spirituality develops one's personality" is the competency with the lowest mean of 2.40, described as "least-mastered." In the interview conducted by the researcher, it was revealed that some students are busy doing activities like social media Facebook, Twitter, or Instagram. Most boys engaged primarily in playing Mobile Legend, Dota, or Clash of Clans, wherein the spiritual concept in life is taken for granted. Attending church, attending prayer meetings, and praying the Holy Rosary for Roman Catholics are seldom done.

Spirituality is indeed essential. It can be inferred that faith is trust in God. Many believe that there is a God who directs all our affairs. Trust in God does not come from an individual. One may believe more deeply than one, but they both have it. This is important because no matter how small a person is, he or she still hopes that God can help and forgive his or her sin no matter how lowly he/she may be. As one develops his faith, he creates goodness and follows the path of holiness and the inculcation of values. This backs up Schwartz's (2012) claim that values have been a central concept in the social sciences since their inception.

As shown in the table, the second to the lowest competency, which has a mean of 2.84, is "Promote compliance with national and international laws." This implies that the students tend to neglect laws and regulations in school and the community, like waste segregation, proper garbage disposal, vandalism, burning, and conserving water and electricity. In the

informal interview, students stated that they do not follow simple rules and regulations because their elders are not doing the right thing. Bad modeling among adults causes them to be irresponsible in following rules and regulations.

Consequently, in a society where people live under the law, everyone needs to know what he or she is doing and why he or she is doing so. Every citizen must understand that law enforcement depends on the cooperation of each person. Some citizens cannot obey and obey the law, while others will disobey it. When this happens, indeed, any dream, we, for the people, will probably not yield as expected. Everyone must work together to enforce national and international laws better. As a young child, obeying the laws of home, school, and the community is a great thing to eventually becoming a good and law-abiding citizen.

Moreover, Alonzo (2015) emphasizes that Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao, in the classroom setting, sets according to the ever-changing needs of society and the nation. Educational systems and teachers attempt to meet them and have an essential role in the individual build-up and setting the life patterns of which values are one of the components.

Discussion

This study determined the level of mastery of competencies of the learners in ESP of Grade 6 students. Specifically, it described the learning competencies of Grade 6 students in Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao (ESP) and the level of students' competencies as reflected in their manifestation of the intended ESP Curriculum.

A cross-sectional descriptive design was used with the Curriculum Guide of the K to 12 Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao Grade 6 (2016) competencies as part of the questionnaire's content. The questionnaire was supplemented with interviews to verify the responses of the respondents. The questionnaire was piloted before being distributed to the 105 Grade 6 students from the selected public elementary schools in the Ubay III, Southwest District. In the analysis and interpretation of data on ESP competencies, weighted mean and one-way analysis of variance were used.

After retrieving the questionnaire, the gathered data were tallied, collated, and illustrated through tables. The needed data were statistically analyzed and interpreted.

As an offshoot of the study, an enhancement scheme on the awareness of spiritual development and compliance with national and international laws of the students was designed. Seminar workshops, spiritual recollection, and other related activities were provided for the students' values development.

Conclusion

With the findings being established, the researcher arrived at the following conclusions: (1) Students have gained mastery of the competencies. Competencies are manifested by the students regardless of their geographical locations. A strong foundation of values education at home, in school, and the community is vital in the formation of the students. Those values have to be acted upon and practiced by the students. Moreover, awareness of one's spiritual development helps every individual become God-fearing and contemplate the church's good teachings and dogmas.

Moreover, it is highly recommended that: (1) The proposed enhancement scheme on the awareness of spiritual development of the students and the compliance of national and international laws should be realized in order for the students to build a strong foundation of values and attitudes to become lifelong learners. (2) There is a need for the students to be aware of the implementation of these competencies. Teachers should make sure that the pupils internalize ESP competencies. Mastery should include the application of the concepts learned in real-life situations. Students need to attend recollections and retreats. (3) Parents are recommended to attend a seminar-workshop on values education to be more aware of some strategies to mold their children at home and how good manners should be practiced by the children. (4) Students need to internalize and practice the values—School and school administrators must ensure that all competencies are taken seriously. The time allotment for ESP subject should be used for discussing the competencies, not for cleaning the school and other related activities. (5) There is a need to strengthen collaboration amongst everyone in the educational system, and ESP is a major subject. DepEd officials should devise plans and activities to improve ESP instruction. Increase supervision of teachers' teaching methods and constantly monitor every student's values formation. There is also a need for future teachers to go into validation of the findings by researching actual observations.

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